

THE DEFINITION OF LOVE IN THE DEVON OF ERKIN VAHIDOV

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Abstract. The theme of love has long been one of the main themes of classical literature. The origin and development of the ghazal genre goes back to the need to express the feelings of people and their love. Romantic gazelles also dominate Erkin Vakhidov's divan, such as the ones of Atoyι, Lutfiy, Navoi. The article analyzes romantic ghazals and examples written about love.

Keywords:love, dominance, divine love, lyrical hero, hyperbole, classical literature, figurative love, gazelle.

The theme of love is one of the eternal themes of Uzbek classic literature, and it occupies a central place in the lyrics of almost every artist. There is a human race whose heart is naturally occupied by various emotions. Especially poets express their love, hatred, admiration and sometimes anger through poetry. The theme of love is the leading theme in the works of Atoyι, Lutfiy, and Navoi even now. In particular, Alisher Navoi divided love into three types in his work "Mahbub ul-Qulub":

1. Public love.
2. Special's love.
3. The love of the Siddiqs. [1.52]

If we look for the dictionary meaning of the word Ishq, this word is derived from the Arabic word ``ashqa", and ``ashqa" is a plant that grows like a weed. This symbolic meaning means that love is wrapped around the human heart like a blanket. According to Ghazali, the highest level of love is called love. And Yassavi says that work is both pain and medicine, both pain and pleasure." [4,43]

From the point of view of classical literature, romantic ghazals are analyzed in two aspects: divine love and metaphorical love. Divine love expresses the love of God by its name, and the love of a slave to a slave is called metaphorical love. Divine

love was the leader in classic literary masterpieces until the 20th century. But by the end of the century figurative love began to dominate. Different poets described the feeling of love in different ways. Hazrat Navoi, while talking about love, said:

*If there is no love, there will be no two worlds,
So there are two worlds, no soul. [3,143]*

Definitions have changed over time. Each poet expressed love in his own way. The works of Erkin Vahidov, Abdulla Oripov, Amon Matjonlar are among them. Especially "Yoshlik Devano", a compilation of Erkin Vahidov's ghazals, is distinguished by its special hymn of love. The poet himself said about it in one of his ghazals:

*People of poetry may open the verse of my book as love.
No, my book is a prelude to the court of love.[2,104]*

In the poet's ghazals, the concept of love is found in many places, and some ghazals are built on the purpose of describing this feeling. For example, the following is said about love in the radiative ghazal "Shirin":

*The pain of love is foreign only to the unloved,
When there is love, even sorrow is sweet when parting.[2,89]*

Indeed, where there is love, there is pain. This pain is alien to the loveless. But to a person who has true love in his heart, the sadness that comes after parting feels sweet. Love in the heart has been likened to a burning fire by poets since ancient times. But Erkin Vahidov exaggerates this analogy:

*They say that the fire of love makes even the sun shine.
If it wants to warm, let the sun come to my heart.[2,109]*

The fact that the sun is made of fire has been scientifically proven. But the lover's heart is burning so much with the fire of love that even the sun is cold in front of him. Such an image reflects the poet's artistic skill.

Some of Erkin Vahidov's ghazals are completely devoted to the definition of love. One of them is called "Love". If we pay attention to some verses of the ghazal:

*Love is so kind that it blooms from a thorn,
He devotes his soul to the stone and makes the nightingale also.*

*Love is such a pain that all parts are affected,
When a madman does something, a madman likes it.*

*Love is such a god that it is equal to a king, a gado,
A king is a sultan who deceives a slave, and a king becomes a slave if he is deceived*
[2,99]

The first description shows the beautiful aspects of love: love is like a spring, it makes flowers grow from thorns, it makes nightingales grow from thorns. But in the next stanza, the consequences of love are discussed: love is a pain that affects everyone, and the one that is affected is the heart. This pain does not choose a king or a gado, whoever suffers from this pain, if he is a king, becomes a slave to his love, and a gado can imagine the kingdom in his heart. It can be said that this is the most objective definition given to love by poets. The next ghazal is called "Izhori ishq". It shows the situation of a lyrical hero in love. For example:

*For the first time, the heart suddenly felt love called pain,
Who told you about pain, love is the medicine for my pain.*

*Death in love is suffering, or death without love is suffering,
The heart is like love, even though love is painful.[2,110]*

As the poet writes about love, whose act is pain and which is also the cure for this pain, "is it more painful to be in love, or to live without love?" raises the question and tells the answer himself: no matter how much the heart hurts from love, it is forced to love. So, the heart of the heart is love, without which the heart cannot be at peace.

Every poet is in love in his heart. To write a romantic ghazal, you need to have love in your heart. In his ghazals, Erkin Vahidov touched upon the definition of love and the difficulties of putting it down on paper. In particular, the ghazal "Dostonga Yaz" in the Divan covers the same topic. We analyze its following bytes:

*Come, describe the pleasure of love and write it in the epic,
Sew each line of flowers on a piece of paper.*

*The flower of the world is not enough for the poem of love,
Write a comment of love in the sky with a light pen.*

*The definition of the pain of love is the ink of the heart's blood,
Write the word charming on the heart, write the word joon on the soul. [2.75]*

The pain of love has been described by many. But in the opinion of Erkin Vahidov, this description should be written as an epic, and every verse should be written in one piece. The problem is that the world is not enough to write this epic, so it is better to write it with light in the infinite sky. If love is real, its pain will also make the heart bleed. The poet advises to use this blood as ink. It is also known from the verses that writing the pain of love is a responsible thing. If we look at history, there have been many people who have written about love. Some of them repeated each other. But the original verses have not fallen out of the people's language for centuries.

We can say that Erkin Vahidov's verses are eternal. Because real feelings are expressed in them, there is no fakeness or artificiality involved. Everything is an expression of the delicate feelings of the poet's heart. We can cite the following stanza as proof of our opinion:

*You are a poem about love, free, not without reason, love
Every now and then, he keeps his mind busy with poetry. [2,100]*

So, it is not without reason that the poet writes about love, when love occupies the heart, it makes a person busy with poetry. That's probably why even the most serious people who fall in love end up writing a few lines and become poets. Erkin Vahidov's divan will live forever in hearts because it expresses sincere feelings.

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